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STATISTICAL DIGITAL SIGNAL PROCESSING

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PROJECT TITLE:

An Integrated Yolo-Kalman-Hungarian System (YKHS) For Real-Time and Offline Object Detection, Tracking, And Counting': A PYTHON-BASED APPROACH

TEAM

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 BRIEF OVERVIEW

In today's digital world, especially in computer vision, videos are not just for entertainment but are also tools powering real-time decisions in several areas, such as sports analytics, autonomous vehicles, traffic monitoring, and surveillance. Accurate and efficient object tracking plays a vital role in the above-mentioned real-world applications because the functionality and accuracy of these systems rely on their ability to detect and track objects as they move through a scene. In this scenario, a system must be able to understand what is happening, react to it, and then predict what might come next. This can be very challenging, especially in real time.

Modern object detectors like YOLOv8 are impressively accurate at identifying objects in video frames but fall short when it comes to tracking objects occasionally. This project aims to develop a hybrid system that combines object detection with prediction and data association to offer a reliable object-tracking solution.

The primary focus of this project is to critically observe and evaluate the performance of the Kalman filter with this integrated tracking pipeline, especially in verifying its prediction accuracy, adaptive correction, and stability over time. This project examined real-time and offline modes to observe Kalman filter behavior in tracking applications. This project's contribution is further supported by data visualization, statistical analysis, and performance metrics such as ID consistency, Intersection over Union (IoU), Kalman gain behavior, and Mean Square Error (MSE).

This integrated approach will strengthen the temporal continuity in object tracking and provide an in-depth understanding of how Kalman filtering enhances the accuracy and reliability of deep learning-based detection in dynamic scenes.

Problem Statement

The need for systems capable of concise detection, tracking, and counting multiple objects in video streams is increasing, particularly in real-time situations like traffic surveillance, monitoring, and sports analysis. Nevertheless, real-time object tracking encounters challenges such as noisy detections, occlusions, re-identifying objects, and temporary visibility loss. These issues can lead to unstable or inconsistent tracking.

Motivation

In today's world, video surveillance and analytics play a crucial role in security, sports analysis, traffic management, and automation. However, this goes beyond just identifying the presence and location of objects in individual frames that make up the video. The most important thing in security systems built for such purposes is understanding how those objects move over time, maintaining their identities, and filtering out noise that can cause confusion or errors because accuracy is essential in many real-world applications.

Objectives

- To build a reliable object tracking system by combining YOLOv8 for object detection, a Kalman filter for motion prediction and noise smoothing, and the Hungarian algorithm to correctly match detections with existing tracks. Relying solely on object detection without incorporating multi-object tracking would fall short in handling many real-world challenges, such as object occlusions, variations in appearance, and objects temporarily entering or leaving the frame.
- To evaluate the performance of the Kalman filter in the tracking process, specifically how well it maintains object identity to provide stable, consistent tracking across real-time and offline video analysis.

2.0 METHODOLOGIES

This project utilizes a modular approach for detecting objects, tracking their movement, and assessing performance. The selected methods are as follows. The most essential parts of this project are the YOLO Object detection model, Kalman Filter Algorithm, and Hungarian Algorithm. In this section, the reasons behind the choice of each of these methods are carefully discussed.

Figure 1: Essential Parts of the Project

1. Object Detection with YOLOv8:

YOLO (You-Only-Look-Once) is a well-known object detector that performs frame-wise object detection by drawing bounding boxes around object classes identified in each video frame. YOLO is an essential part of this project and is considered for use because of its accuracy and fast detection capability. Although it has a high object detection accuracy, it still lacks temporal consistency and cannot track object identities over time. The version of YOLO used in this project is YOLOv8, one of the fastest and most accurate object detectors. This detector is pre-trained with the COCO dataset, which has 80 object categories (classes) used for detection and segmentation tasks, and with over 200,000 images.

Table 1: COCO Dataset Class Categories and Class Names

Super category	Number of Classes	Class Names
Person	1	person
Vehicle	8	bicycle, car, motorcycle, airplane, bus, train, truck, boat
Outdoor	5	traffic light, fire hydrant, stop sign, parking meter, bench
Animal	10	bird, cat, dog, horse, sheep, cow, elephant, bear, zebra, giraffe
Accessory	5	backpack, umbrella, handbag, tie, suitcase
Sports	10	frisbee, skis, snowboard, sports ball, kite, baseball bat, baseball glove, skateboard, surfboard, tennis racket
Kitchen	7	bottle, wine glass, cup, fork, knife, spoon, bowl
Food	11	banana, apple, sandwich, orange, broccoli, carrot, hot dog, pizza, donut, cake
Furniture	6	chair, couch, potted plant, bed, dining table, toilet
Electronic	6	tv, laptop, mouse, remote, keyboard, cell phone
Appliance	5	microwave, oven, toaster, sink, refrigerator
Indoor	6	book, clock, vase, scissors, teddy bear, toothbrush

Figure 2: YOLO-based Detection of Pet Animals

2. Object Tracking Using Kalman Filter

Since this project is focused on real-time and offline modes, the Kalman filter is considered the best for use because it is a recursive estimator that can use previous measurements to predict the future states of a dynamic system. It is also a choice for solving many problems, such as smoothing, prediction, interpolation, and deconvolution. This filter is also a shift-varying type and is well-suited for stationary and non-stationary processes. Unlike the Wiener filter, which is a linear shift-invariant filter capable of estimating stationary processes. This project employs a Kalman filter to smooth out noisy detection, carefully treat object motion across frames, and estimate the object position in the next frame (even if it is not detected). The Kalman filter recursively finds the best estimates and maintains consistent state variables such as position, velocity, width, and height. Kalman filter's exceptional ability to handle occlusion makes it a reliable choice for tracking purposes with excellent predictions.

How does it work?

The Kalman filter uses a predictive motion model to ensure stable and less jittery tracking over time. This ensures that noise originating from the anYOLO detection stage is significantly reduced.

Step 1: Kalman Filter Prediction Step

Kalman filter prediction is the first step of the Kalman filtering process. The algorithm relies on a mathematical model of the system's temporal evolution to estimate the next state of the system, before receiving any new measurements. These steps form the "a priori" estimate before any measurement is incorporated.

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^- = \mathbf{A}\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k-1} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}_k \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

Eq.1 predicts the next state estimate based on the previous estimate and optional control input.

$$\mathbf{P}_k^- = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{P}_{k-1}\mathbf{A}^\top + \mathbf{Q} \quad (\text{eq. 2})$$

Eq. 2 predicts the covariance estimate (uncertainty of the next state), factoring in previous uncertainty and model noise.

Step 2: Correction (Update Step)

After the prediction step, the Kalman Filter receives a new measurement and uses it to improve the accuracy of its predicted state. This step corrects the predicted estimate based on how close it is to the actual observation. These steps repeat at each time step to produce an optimal solution while recursively filtering out noise.

$$\mathbf{K}_k = \mathbf{P}_k \mathbf{H}^T (\mathbf{H} \mathbf{P}_k \mathbf{H}^T + \mathbf{R})^{-1} \quad (\text{eq. 3})$$

Eq. 3 computes the Kalman Gain \mathbf{K}_k , which balances trust between the model prediction and the new measurement.

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^- + \mathbf{K}_k (\mathbf{z}_k - \mathbf{H} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^-) \quad (\text{eq. 4})$$

Eq. 4 updates the predicted state ($\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^-$) using the new measurement \mathbf{z}_k . The innovation term ($\mathbf{z}_k - \mathbf{H} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^-$) captures the measurement error, which is scaled by the Kalman Gain to correct the prediction.

$$\mathbf{P}_k = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_k \mathbf{H}) \mathbf{P}_k^- \quad (\text{eq. 5})$$

Eq. 5 updates the error covariance, reflecting how confident the filter is in the corrected state estimate.

Where,

Previous estimated state ($\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k-1}$) -> The best guess of the system's state at time $k-1$, **Control input matrix** (\mathbf{B}) -> describes how external control input affects the state, **Control vector/input** (\mathbf{u}_k) -> optional known input (e.g., steering, acceleration) applied at the time, **State transition matrix** (\mathbf{A}) -> defines how the current state evolves to the next one without measurement., **Updated (posterior) state estimate** ($\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k$) -> best estimate of the state after measurement correction, **Predicted (prior) state estimate** ($\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^-$) -> estimate before correction using the new measurement. **Kalman Gain** (\mathbf{K}_k) -> determines how much weight to give to the new measurement versus the prediction, **Predicted error covariance** (\mathbf{P}_k^-) -> uncertainty in the state prediction (from the prediction step), **Observation matrix** (\mathbf{H}) -> maps the predicted state to the measurement space, \mathbf{H}^T -> Transpose of the observation matrix, **Measurement noise covariance** (\mathbf{R}) -> how much noise is expected in the measurements, **Measurement at time k** (\mathbf{z}_k) -> The actual observed value at this time step, **Identity matrix** (\mathbf{I}) -> ensures proper dimensionality in matrix operations. **Updated error covariance** (\mathbf{P}_k) -> updated uncertainty after incorporating the measurement.

Table 2: Summary of Kalman Filter Parameters and Operations based on implementation setup in this project

<pre>self.kf.A = np.array([[1, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0], # cx = cx + v_{cx} [0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0], # cy = cy + v_{cy} [0, 0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 1], # w = w + vw [0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0, 0], # h = h (constant) [0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0], # v_{cx} remains [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0], # v_{cy} remains [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1], # v_w remains])</pre> <p>A (State transition matrix)</p>	<pre>self.kf.H = np.array([[1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0], [0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0], [0, 0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0], [0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0, 0],])</pre> <p>H (Observation matrix)</p>	<p>B = 0, u_k = 0</p> <p>Control Input (B, u_k)</p> <p>P* = 3</p> <p>Initial Error Covariance (P)</p>	<p>R* = 10</p> <p>Measurement Noise Covariance (R)</p> <p>scaled default: Q* = 1</p> <p>Process Noise Covariance (Q)</p>
<pre>self.k_gain = (float(self.kf.K[0, 0]), float(self.kf.K[1, 1]))</pre> <p>Kalman Gain (K_k), this is auto-calculated</p>	<pre>self.kf.x[:4] = np.array([[x], [y], [w], [h]])</pre> <p>State Vector (x)</p>		
<pre>bbox.reshape((4, 1))</pre> <p>Measurements (z_k); Passed as reshaped 4x1:</p>	<pre>self.kf.predict()</pre> <p>Prediction</p>	<pre>self.kf.update(...)</pre> <p>Correction / Update</p>	

3. Data Association Using Hungarian Algorithm (Kuhn Munkres)

This algorithm is considered a combinational optimization method capable of matching current detection to existing tracks by minimizing the global assignment cost. It is very useful in finding optimal assignments between two sets of elements. Since this project requires matching objects in the current frame with their track IDs from the existing frame, maintaining the identities of these objects across consecutive frames is essential. The Hungarian algorithm helps correctly associate data even when these objects are temporarily occluded or undetected.

The Hungarian algorithm uses cost minimization (e.g., based on 1- IoU) to assign bounding boxes to the right existing Kalman tracks. This method ensures optimal matching between predicted and detected objects, preventing ID switching.

Overall, the need for a method that can tell whether an obstacle from one frame is the same as in another frame makes the Hungarian algorithm a key component of this project. Although its demerit is the Polynomial-time complexity because it has a worst-time complexity of $O(N^3)$. Where N is the number of objects. As the number of objects increases, the time required to find the optimal assignment grows significantly.

Figure 3: Hungarian Algorithm in Action

Why IoU is vital in Hungarian Algorithm?

IoU is an essential metric for evaluating object detection and prediction accuracy. To tell how a model predicts an object's location, IoU compares the detection bounding box (from YOLO) with the predicted bounding box (from Kalman Filter). The higher the IoU, the better the prediction accuracy.

$$IoU = \frac{\text{Area of Overlap}}{\text{Area of Union}}$$

Figure 4: IoU

Table 3: IoU Thresholds for Object Matching and Interpretation

IoU Score	Interpretation	Matching Action
≤ 0.3	Poor overlap (likely wrong object)	No match
$0.4 - 0.6$	Moderate overlap (partial hit)	Match if tolerance allows
≥ 0.7	Good to excellent match	Likely match

4. Performance Evaluation Metrics

- **Mean Squared Error (MSE):** This metric determines the deviation between YOLO detection and Kalman filter predictions by averaging their squared differences. Lower MSE values imply higher prediction accuracy.
- **Intersection over Union (IoU):** Evaluates the overlap between YOLO detection boxes and those predicted by Kalman. Spatial alignment increases as values approach 1.
- **Pearson Correlation:** Evaluates the linear relationship between detection and prediction values (e.g., center x, center y, width, and height). A strong correlation indicates consistent tracking behavior.
- **Time Series Comparison Plot:** Illustrates how detection and prediction values (such as center coordinates, width, and height) change over frames. It provides an understanding of the temporal consistency and the prediction lag or drift.

These metrics confirm the fidelity of Kalman filter predictions to actual YOLO measurements, always ensuring reliable tracking and alignment time.

3.0 IMPLEMENTATION

This section shows a comprehensive implementation approach to this project's object detection, tracking, and counting system. This section is essential in this project because it helps provide a clear and concise description of how we developed and integrated the YOLO, Kalman filter, and Hungarian algorithm for object tracking. This section covers a lot of procedures and features, which will be discussed as follows.

A. Yolo Model Detection

Model Selection: We chose YOLOv8 for object detection in this project due to its exceptional balance between accuracy and computational efficiency. This model was pre-trained on a large COCO dataset and fine-tuned for specific object classes.

Detection Thresholds: To ensure that only reliable detections are used for tracking, a confidence threshold of 0.5 was set to filter out low-confidence detections.

Bounding Box Representation: YOLO detections were represented as bounding boxes with center coordinates (x, y), width, and height.

B. Kalman Filter

- **State Estimation:** The state of each tracked object was estimated using the Kalman filter. This includes position (x, y), velocity (Vx and Vy), and dimensions (width, height).
- **State Transition Model:** A constant velocity model was also chosen in this project, assuming that objects move with constant velocity between frames.
- **Measurement Model:** This project also selected a measurement model to relate the state of objects to measurements from YOLO detections.
- **Covariance Matrices:** To ensure optimal performance, this project ensures that the process noise covariance matrix (Q) and measurement covariance Matrix (R) are carefully tuned.

C. Data Association

- **Hungarian Algorithm:** To accurately associate YOLO detections with existing tracks, this project employed a Hungarian algorithm, which minimizes the cost matrix based on IoU (Intersection over Union) values.
- **IoU Threshold:** To correctly determine whether a detection matches an existing track, an IoU threshold of 0.1 was set in this project. The detection is considered a match if the IoU value exceeds this threshold.
- **Cost Matrix Computation:** In our case, the IoU values between detections and tracks compute the cost matrix.

Track Management

- **Track Initialization:** The Initial state of the track is set based on the detection. So, when detection is not associated with an existing track, new tracks would be initialized.
- **Track Update:** The algorithm uses the Kalman filter to estimate the state of the object to update existing tracks with new detections
- **Track Termination:** After a maximum number of frames without an associated detection has been reached, the tracks will be terminated indicating that the object is no longer present.

Additional Features

- **Data Logging:** Tracking data is logged into a CSV file. This includes information such as tracking ID, detection index, bounding box coordinates for detections, Kalman filter prediction data, corrected/updated data, IoU, and fusion technique results data.
- **Visualization:** OpenCV is used to display tracking results, which include the bounding boxes, track IDs, and velocities. Matplotlib and Seaborn are used to create informative and attractive statistical graphics.

Flowchart of the System

Figure 5: Flowchart of the System

4.0 RESULTS & DISCUSSION

In this project, we consider two different scenarios: Real-time and offline object tracking modes. In a real-time scenario, a computer camera (Webcam) was used to gather live video of objects, and the algorithm was run on this live video in real-time to observe the accuracy and reliability of the YOLO + Kalman + Hungarian algorithm in Object detection, counting, and tracking applications. In the offline scenario, we applied the algorithm on a prerecorded video file to see the effectiveness of our approach, especially the Kalman filter, and whether its predictions and corrections are mostly reliable.

We also observed the behavior of this object-tracking algorithm by using several metrics to confirm its performance, accuracy, and reliability. These metrics include *Intersection over Union (IoU)*, *Normalized Mean Squared Error (MSE)*, *Pearson Correlation Coefficient*, *Visual Time Series Plots*, and *Kalman Gain Values*.

CASE 1: Real-time Object Tracking Mode

Figure 6: Case 1 Live Video Tested

Frame	Track_ID	Detection...	Label	YOLO_CX	YOLO_CY	YOLO_W	YOLO_H	Kalman_CX	Kalman_CY	Kalman_W	Kalman_H	IoU	Kx	Ky	Corrected_CX	Corrected_CY	Corrected_W	Corrected_H	Fused_CX	Fused_CY	Fused_W	Fused_H
0	0	0	person	285.5	309.0	353.0	340.0	286.0	309.0	354.0	340.0	0.9972	0.4118	0.4118	285.75	309.0	353.5	340.0	285.79	309.0	353.59	340.0
0	0	0	person	287.5	309.0	353.0	340.0	285.71	309.0	353.41	340.0	0.9899	0.5479	0.5479	286.6	309.0	353.21	340.0	286.69	309.0	353.19	340.0
0	0	0	person	287.5	309.0	353.0	340.0	287.03	309.0	352.91	340.0	0.9973	0.5909	0.5909	287.26	309.0	352.96	340.0	287.31	309.0	352.96	340.0
0	0	0	person	285.0	309.0	354.0	340.0	287.75	309.0	352.71	340.0	0.9845	0.5908	0.5908	286.38	309.0	353.36	340.0	286.13	309.0	353.47	340.0
0	0	0	person	285.0	309.0	352.0	340.0	285.98	309.0	353.49	340.0	0.9945	0.5837	0.5837	285.49	309.0	352.75	340.0	285.41	309.0	352.62	340.0
0	0	0	person	287.0	309.0	352.0	340.0	285.06	309.0	352.34	340.0	0.989	0.5793	0.5793	286.03	309.0	352.17	340.0	286.18	309.0	352.14	340.0
0	0	0	person	286.0	309.0	354.0	340.0	286.23	309.0	351.79	340.0	0.9937	0.5779	0.5779	286.12	309.0	352.89	340.0	286.1	309.0	353.07	340.0
0	0	0	person	286.5	309.0	351.0	340.0	286.1	309.0	353.16	340.0	0.9939	0.5777	0.5777	286.3	309.0	352.08	340.0	286.33	309.0	351.91	340.0
0	0	0	person	287.0	309.0	352.0	340.0	286.41	309.0	351.57	340.0	0.9967	0.5779	0.5779	286.71	309.0	351.78	340.0	286.75	309.0	351.82	340.0
0	0	0	person	287.5	309.0	355.0	340.0	286.96	309.0	351.56	340.0	0.9903	0.5781	0.5781	287.23	309.0	353.28	340.0	287.27	309.0	353.55	340.0
0	0	0	person	286.0	309.0	354.0	340.0	287.59	309.0	354.0	340.0	0.9911	0.5781	0.5781	286.79	309.0	354.0	340.0	286.67	309.0	354.0	340.0
0	0	0	person	286.5	308.5	353.0	341.0	286.66	309.0	354.45	340.0	0.993	0.5781	0.5781	286.58	308.75	353.72	340.5	286.57	308.71	353.61	340.27
0	0	0	person	287.5	309.0	353.0	340.0	286.52	308.61	353.76	340.27	0.9922	0.5781	0.5781	287.01	308.8	353.38	340.14	287.09	308.83	353.32	340.2
0	0	0	person	288.0	309.0	354.0	340.0	287.25	308.81	353.32	340.2	0.9946	0.5781	0.5781	287.62	308.91	353.66	340.1	287.68	308.92	353.71	340.14
0	0	0	person	287.5	309.0	355.0	340.0	287.99	308.94	353.85	340.14	0.9963	0.5781	0.5781	287.75	308.97	354.42	340.07	287.71	308.97	354.51	340.11
0	0	0	person	287.0	308.5	354.0	341.0	287.92	309.0	354.89	340.11	0.9919	0.5781	0.5781	287.46	308.75	354.44	340.55	287.39	308.71	354.37	340.35
0	0	0	person	286.0	308.5	352.0	341.0	287.41	308.64	354.56	340.35	0.9902	0.5781	0.5781	286.7	308.57	353.28	340.67	286.59	308.56	353.08	340.52
0	0	0	person	286.5	308.5	349.0	341.0	286.33	308.46	352.75	340.52	0.988	0.5781	0.5781	286.41	308.48	350.87	340.76	286.43	308.48	350.58	340.65
0	0	0	person	286.0	308.5	354.0	341.0	286.2	308.39	349.47	340.65	0.9862	0.5781	0.5781	286.1	308.44	351.74	340.83	286.08	308.45	352.09	340.75
0	0	0	person	287.0	308.5	352.0	341.0	285.81	308.38	351.91	340.75	0.9925	0.5781	0.5781	286.41	308.44	351.96	340.87	286.5	308.45	351.96	340.81
0	0	0	person	287.0	308.5	354.0	341.0	286.47	308.4	351.81	340.81	0.9932	0.5781	0.5781	286.74	308.45	352.9	340.91	286.78	308.46	353.07	340.86
0	0	0	person	287.0	308.5	350.0	341.0	286.86	308.43	353.37	340.86	0.9901	0.5781	0.5781	286.93	308.47	351.68	340.93	286.94	308.47	351.42	340.9
0	0	0	person	288.0	308.5	348.0	341.0	287.05	308.46	351.02	340.9	0.9911	0.5781	0.5781	286.53	308.48	349.51	340.95	286.44	308.48	349.27	340.93
0	0	0	person	286.0	307.5	352.0	343.0	286.34	308.48	348.25	340.93	0.9834	0.5781	0.5781	287.17	307.99	350.13	341.96	287.3	307.91	350.42	341.49
0	0	0	person	287.5	308.0	351.0	342.0	287.53	307.71	350.17	341.49	0.9959	0.5781	0.5781	287.52	307.85	350.58	341.74	287.51	307.88	350.65	341.63
0	0	0	person	286.0	307.5	352.0	343.0	287.74	307.73	350.57	341.63	0.9862	0.5781	0.5781	286.87	307.62	351.28	342.31	286.74	307.6	351.4	342.0
0	0	0	person	287.0	308.0	350.0	342.0	286.61	307.4	351.61	342.0	0.992	0.5781	0.5781	286.8	307.7	350.81	342.0	286.83	307.75	350.68	342.0
0	0	0	person	286.0	307.5	352.0	343.0	286.79	307.68	350.56	342.0	0.9926	0.5781	0.5781	286.39	307.59	351.28	342.5	286.33	307.58	351.39	342.27
0	0	0	person	285.0	308.0	348.0	342.0	286.12	307.47	351.57	342.27	0.9868	0.5781	0.5781	285.56	307.73	349.79	342.13	285.47	307.78	349.51	342.2
0	0	0	person	285.5	307.5	349.0	343.0	285.03	307.78	348.95	342.2	0.995	0.5781	0.5781	285.27	307.64	348.98	342.6	285.3	307.62	348.98	342.41
0	0	0	person	287.5	307.5	351.0	343.0	284.96	307.56	348.43	342.41	0.9839	0.5781	0.5781	286.23	307.53	349.72	342.71	286.43	307.53	349.92	342.57
0	0	0	person	285.5	308.0	345.0	342.0	286.61	307.46	349.9	342.57	0.9829	0.5781	0.5781	286.05	307.73	347.45	342.29	285.97	307.77	347.07	342.42
0	0	0	person	285.0	308.0	348.0	342.0	285.92	307.82	346.04	342.42	0.9932	0.5781	0.5781	285.46	307.91	347.02	342.21	285.39	307.92	347.17	342.3
0	0	0	person	285.0	308.0	348.0	342.0	285.15	308.0	346.55	342.3	0.995	0.5781	0.5781	285.07	308.0	347.28	342.15	285.06	308.0	347.39	342.22
0	0	0	person	285.5	307.5	349.0	343.0	284.79	308.08	347.06	342.22	0.9911	0.5781	0.5781	285.15	307.79	348.03	342.61	285.2	307.75	348.18	342.43
0	0	0	person	286.5	308.0	349.0	342.0	285.08	307.71	348.26	342.43	0.9902	0.5781	0.5781	285.79	307.85	348.63	342.22	285.9	307.88	348.69	342.32
0	0	0	person	286.0	308.0	348.0	342.0	286.07	307.9	348.91	342.32	0.9965	0.5781	0.5781	286.03	307.95	348.46	342.16	286.03	307.96	348.38	342.23
0	0	0	person	285.5	308.0	347.0	342.0	286.18	308.0	348.42	342.23	0.9952	0.5781	0.5781	285.84	308.0	347.71	342.12	285.79	308.0	347.6	342.17
0	0	0	person	284.0	308.0	348.0	342.0	285.8	308.04	347.35	342.17	0.9892	0.5781	0.5781	284.9	308.02	347.67	342.08	284.76	308.02	347.72	342.12

Figure 7: Case 1 Summary of Detection, Predicted, Corrected, IoU, Kalman gain values, etc.

Figure 8: Case 1 Time Series Comparison Plots


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✓ Loaded latest CSV file: iou_tracking_data_20250418_194009.csv

===== Normalized MSE Summary =====
MSE (Center X): 0.000017
MSE (Center Y): 0.000040
MSE (Width): 0.000041
MSE (Height): 0.000175
Overall Normalized MSE: 0.000068

```

Figure 10: Case 1 Summary of MSE Values

Figure 9: Case 1 Pearson's Correlation Between YOLO, Kalman, Corrected, and Fused Variables

CASE 2: Offline Object Tracking Mode (Pre-recorded Video Object Tracking Test 1)

Figure 11: Case 2 Test 1 Pre-recorded Video Tested

Frame	Track_ID	Detectio...	Label	YOLO_CX	YOLO_CY	YOLO_W	YOLO_H	Kalman_CX	Kalman_CY	Kalman_W	Kalman_H	IoU	Kx	Ky	Corrected_CX	Corrected_CY	Corrected_W	Corrected_H	Fused_CX	Fused_CY	Fused_W	Fused_H
0	0	0	person	278.5	262.5	45.0	87.0	267.5	263.0	29.0	90.0	0.5306	0.4118	0.4118	273.0	262.75	37.0	88.5	272.03	262.79	35.59	89.14
0	1	1	person	657.5	282.0	47.0	82.0	661.5	281.5	43.0	83.0	0.8279	0.4118	0.4118	659.5	281.75	45.0	82.5	659.85	281.71	44.65	82.71
0	2	2	person	514.0	194.5	32.0	73.0	514.5	193.5	31.0	75.0	0.9437	0.4118	0.4118	514.25	194.0	31.5	74.0	514.29	193.91	31.41	74.43
0	3	3	truck	687.0	71.5	70.0	55.0	687.0	71.5	70.0	55.0	1.0	0.4118	0.4118	687.0	71.5	70.0	55.0	687.0	71.5	70.0	55.0
0	4	4	car	750.5	72.0	33.0	44.0	750.5	72.0	33.0	44.0	1.0	0.4118	0.4118	750.5	72.0	33.0	44.0	750.5	72.0	33.0	44.0
0	0	0	person	281.5	262.5	47.0	87.0	273.97	262.71	38.41	89.14	0.6873	0.5479	0.5479	277.74	262.6	42.71	88.07	278.1	262.59	43.12	88.55
0	1	1	person	652.5	282.5	41.0	83.0	659.15	281.79	45.35	82.71	0.7225	0.5479	0.5479	655.82	282.15	43.18	82.86	655.51	282.18	42.97	82.79
0	2	2	person	512.0	196.5	32.0	75.0	514.21	194.09	31.59	74.43	0.8191	0.5479	0.5479	513.1	195.29	31.79	74.71	513.0	195.41	31.81	74.59
0	3	3	truck	687.0	71.5	70.0	55.0	687.0	71.5	70.0	55.0	1.0	0.5479	0.5479	687.0	71.5	70.0	55.0	687.0	71.5	70.0	55.0
0	4	4	car	750.5	72.0	33.0	44.0	750.5	72.0	33.0	44.0	1.0	0.5479	0.5479	750.5	72.0	33.0	44.0	750.5	72.0	33.0	44.0
0	0	0	person	290.0	259.0	34.0	88.0	281.82	262.48	47.97	88.55	0.6218	0.5909	0.5909	285.91	260.73	40.99	87.27	286.65	260.41	39.72	87.85
0	2	1	person	508.0	197.0	28.0	78.0	512.39	198.16	32.09	74.59	0.7315	0.5909	0.5909	510.19	196.58	30.04	75.29	509.79	196.66	29.87	74.98
0	3	3	truck	687.0	71.0	70.0	56.0	687.0	71.5	70.0	55.0	0.9821	0.5909	0.5909	687.0	71.25	70.0	55.5	687.0	71.2	70.0	55.27
0	4	4	car	750.5	72.0	33.0	44.0	750.5	72.0	33.0	44.0	1.0	0.5909	0.5909	750.5	72.0	33.0	44.0	750.5	72.0	33.0	44.0
0	0	1	person	297.0	257.0	36.0	86.0	292.25	259.49	41.37	87.85	0.7414	0.5908	0.5908	294.63	258.24	38.69	86.92	295.06	258.02	38.2	87.34
0	2	2	person	505.5	198.5	25.0	75.0	508.18	197.6	29.01	74.98	0.8017	0.5908	0.5908	506.84	198.05	27.01	74.99	506.6	198.13	26.84	74.98
0	3	3	truck	687.0	71.0	70.0	56.0	687.0	71.09	70.0	55.27	0.987	0.5908	0.5908	687.0	71.05	70.0	55.64	687.0	71.04	70.0	55.47
0	4	4	car	750.5	72.0	33.0	44.0	750.5	72.0	33.0	44.0	1.0	0.5908	0.5908	750.5	72.0	33.0	44.0	750.5	72.0	33.0	44.0
0	5	0	person	622.5	282.5	47.0	83.0	633.0	281.0	32.0	84.0	0.5647	0.4118	0.4118	627.75	281.75	39.5	83.5	628.68	281.62	38.18	83.71
0	0	0	person	301.0	255.5	40.0	91.0	301.67	256.58	38.7	87.34	0.9276	0.5837	0.5837	301.34	256.03	39.35	89.17	301.28	255.94	39.46	88.34
0	2	2	person	501.5	200.5	29.0	77.0	504.41	199.28	25.12	74.98	0.7813	0.5837	0.5837	502.95	199.88	27.06	75.99	502.71	199.99	27.38	75.53
0	3	3	truck	687.0	71.5	70.0	55.0	687.0	70.9	70.0	55.47	0.9786	0.5837	0.5837	687.0	71.2	70.0	55.24	687.0	71.25	70.0	55.34
0	4	4	car	750.5	72.0	33.0	44.0	750.5	72.0	33.0	44.0	1.0	0.5837	0.5837	750.5	72.0	33.0	44.0	750.5	72.0	33.0	44.0
0	0	1	person	617.0	282.5	54.0	85.0	626.82	281.88	40.82	83.71	0.6474	0.5479	0.5479	621.91	282.19	47.41	84.36	621.44	282.22	48.04	84.07
0	0	0	person	306.0	256.0	42.0	88.0	307.76	254.26	40.23	88.34	0.884	0.5793	0.5793	306.88	255.13	41.12	88.17	306.74	255.27	41.26	88.25
0	2	1	person	499.0	202.5	30.0	77.0	499.92	201.38	26.67	75.53	0.8835	0.5793	0.5793	499.46	201.94	28.33	76.26	499.39	202.03	28.6	75.93
0	3	3	truck	687.0	71.5	70.0	55.0	687.0	71.24	70.0	55.34	0.9907	0.5793	0.5793	687.0	71.37	70.0	55.17	687.0	71.39	70.0	55.25
0	4	4	car	750.5	72.0	33.0	44.0	750.5	72.0	33.0	44.0	1.0	0.5793	0.5793	750.5	72.0	33.0	44.0	750.5	72.0	33.0	44.0
0	5	2	person	611.0	281.5	40.0	85.0	617.26	282.63	53.81	84.07	0.7272	0.5909	0.5909	614.13	282.07	46.9	84.54	613.56	281.96	45.65	84.33
0	0	0	person	312.0	255.5	38.0	87.0	312.86	253.94	42.39	88.25	0.8661	0.5779	0.5779	312.43	254.72	40.2	87.62	312.36	254.84	39.85	87.91

Figure 12: Case 2 Test 1 Summary of Detection, Predicted, Corrected, IoU, Kalman gain values, etc.

Figure 13: Case 2 Test 1 Time Series Comparison Plots

Figure 15: Case 2 Test 1 Summary of MSE Values

Figure 14: Case 2 Test 1 Pearson's Correlation Between YOLO, Kalman, Corrected, and Fused Variables

CASE 2: Offline Object Tracking Mode (Pre-recorded Video Object Tracking Test 2)

Figure 16: Case 2 Test 2 Pre-recorded Video Tested

Frame	Track_ID	Detectio...	Label	YOLO_CX	YOLO_CY	YOLO_W	YOLO_H	Kalman_CX	Kalman_CY	Kalman_W	Kalman_H	IoU	Kx	Ky	Corrected_CX	Corrected_CY	Corrected_W	Corrected_H	Fused_CX	Fused_CY	Fused_W	Fused_H
0	0	0	person	808.0	514.0	240.0	436.0	613.0	512.0	220.0	436.0	0.9086	0.4118	0.4118	610.5	513.0	230.0	436.0	610.94	512.82	228.24	436.0
0	1	4	sports ball	687.5	704.5	71.0	69.0	686.0	700.0	76.0	66.0	0.8219	0.4118	0.4118	686.75	702.25	73.5	67.5	686.62	701.85	73.94	66.86
0	2	3	person	1427.0	529.5	302.0	561.0	1417.5	525.0	317.0	574.0	0.9193	0.4118	0.4118	1422.25	527.25	309.5	567.5	1421.41	526.85	310.82	570.29
0	3	5	person	937.5	538.0	181.0	426.0	936.0	537.5	176.0	429.0	0.9858	0.4118	0.4118	936.75	537.75	178.5	427.5	936.62	537.71	178.06	428.14
0	4	1	person	1665.0	557.0	256.0	680.0	1639.0	550.5	296.0	689.0	0.8129	0.4118	0.4118	1652.0	553.75	276.0	684.5	1649.71	553.18	279.53	686.43
0	5	2	person	802.5	544.0	215.0	398.0	810.0	542.0	230.0	400.0	0.9256	0.4118	0.4118	806.25	543.0	222.5	399.0	806.91	542.82	223.82	399.43
0	6	6	person	41.5	430.0	83.0	370.0	31.5	437.5	63.0	367.0	0.7316	0.4118	0.4118	36.5	433.75	73.0	368.5	35.62	434.41	71.24	367.86
0	0	1	person	596.5	513.5	263.0	439.0	610.06	513.18	231.76	436.0	0.8752	0.5479	0.5479	603.28	513.34	247.38	437.5	602.63	513.35	248.88	436.84
0	1	4	sports ball	690.5	706.0	73.0	70.0	686.88	702.65	73.06	66.86	0.8247	0.5479	0.5479	688.69	704.32	73.03	68.43	688.86	704.48	73.03	67.73
0	2	0	person	1441.0	534.0	280.0	554.0	1423.09	527.65	308.18	570.29	0.8602	0.5479	0.5479	1432.04	530.82	294.09	562.14	1432.9	531.13	292.74	565.75
0	3	6	person	936.0	535.5	184.0	421.0	936.88	537.79	178.94	428.14	0.9567	0.5479	0.5479	936.44	536.65	181.47	424.57	936.4	536.54	181.71	426.15
0	4	3	person	1699.5	557.0	233.0	680.0	1654.29	554.32	272.47	686.43	0.6906	0.5479	0.5479	1676.9	555.66	252.74	683.21	1679.06	555.79	250.85	684.64
0	5	2	person	795.0	544.5	204.0	401.0	805.59	543.18	221.18	399.43	0.8996	0.5479	0.5479	800.29	543.84	212.59	400.21	799.79	543.9	211.77	399.87
0	6	5	person	53.5	364.0	107.0	550.0	37.38	433.09	74.76	367.86	0.4673	0.5479	0.5479	45.44	398.54	90.88	458.93	46.21	395.24	92.43	418.56
0	0	1	person	594.0	517.0	292.0	442.0	598.54	513.78	259.8	436.84	0.8769	0.5909	0.5909	596.27	515.39	275.9	439.42	595.86	515.68	278.83	438.25
0	1	7	sports ball	698.5	706.0	73.0	70.0	689.99	706.07	72.13	67.73	0.7688	0.5909	0.5909	694.24	706.04	72.57	68.87	695.02	706.03	72.64	68.35
0	2	0	person	1455.5	538.0	257.0	554.0	1438.82	533.43	283.42	565.75	0.8656	0.5909	0.5909	1447.16	534.71	270.21	559.88	1448.68	534.95	267.61	562.53
0	3	5	person	936.5	536.5	187.0	425.0	936.45	536.08	183.79	426.15	0.9802	0.5909	0.5909	936.48	536.29	185.4	425.58	936.48	536.33	185.69	425.84
0	4	2	person	1737.5	555.0	249.0	680.0	1684.35	557.57	234.44	684.64	0.6927	0.5909	0.5909	1715.92	556.29	241.72	682.32	1719.85	555.05	243.05	683.37
0	5	3	person	784.0	543.5	220.0	485.0	795.96	544.57	205.05	399.87	0.8824	0.5909	0.5909	789.98	544.03	212.53	482.43	788.89	543.94	213.89	481.28
0	6	4	person	62.0	523.5	124.0	873.0	517.9	377.56	103.59	418.56	0.4005	0.5909	0.5909	56.8	450.53	113.79	645.78	57.82	463.8	115.65	543.3
0	7	6	person	1602.0	526.0	158.0	498.0	1592.5	518.0	171.0	504.0	0.9703	0.4118	0.4118	1597.25	522.0	164.5	498.41	1598.41	521.47	165.85	501.71
0	0	1	person	588.5	526.0	311.0	444.0	590.73	518.85	297.12	438.25	0.9419	0.5908	0.5908	589.61	518.43	304.06	441.13	589.41	518.71	305.92	439.82
0	1	7	sports ball	701.0	710.5	72.0	69.0	698.09	707.6	71.95	68.35	0.8502	0.5908	0.5908	698.54	709.05	71.07	68.68	699.01	709.31	71.98	68.53
0	2	0	person	1478.5	538.0	227.0	550.0	1458.41	537.83	252.44	592.53	0.8409	0.5908	0.5908	1467.46	537.82	238.72	556.26	1469.1	537.93	237.41	556.11
0	3	4	person	924.0	536.0	216.0	425.0	936.55	535.97	188.5	425.84	0.9708	0.5908	0.5908	930.27	536.24	202.25	425.42	930.13	536.28	204.75	425.61
0	4	2	person	1777.5	551.5	259.0	689.0	1745.02	557.24	229.98	683.37	0.7639	0.5908	0.5908	1761.26	554.37	244.49	686.18	1764.21	553.85	247.12	684.1
0	5	5	person	782.5	545.0	205.0	408.0	782.32	544.36	210.0	401.28	0.9578	0.5908	0.5908	782.41	544.88	207.8	404.64	782.43	544.74	207.29	403.11
0	6	3	person	70.0	519.0	140.0	873.0	65.74	478.54	131.48	547.3	0.5851	0.5908	0.5908	67.87	499.27	135.74	707.65	68.26	502.88	136.52	632.86
0	7	6	person	1613.0	524.5	170.0	494.0	1608.09	522.53	163.95	501.3	0.8227	0.5479	0.5479	1605.54	523.51	166.68	497.38	1608.26	523.81	166.99	499.29
0	0	1	person	581.0	515.0	318.0	440.0	583.8	520.55	328.59	439.82	0.9407	0.5837	0.5837	582.4	517.78	322.3	439.91	582.17	517.31	321.58	439.87
0	1	6	sports ball	708.0	708.5	68.0	65.0	703.5	711.51	71.29	68.53	0.8043	0.5837	0.5837	705.75	710.0	68.65	66.77	706.13	709.75	68.2	67.57
0	2	4	person	1500.0	536.0	226.0	552.0	1482.71	540.96	216.59	559.11	0.8415	0.5837	0.5837	1491.36	538.43	221.29	555.56	1492.8	538.02	222.08	557.18
0	3	5	person	930.5	536.0	215.0	424.0	928.51	536.04	213.46	425.61	0.9599	0.5837	0.5837	928.51	536.02	214.23	424.8	928.18	536.02	214.36	425.17
0	4	0	person	1785.5	549.5	245.0	689.0	1798.34	553.81	240.28	684.9	0.9688	0.5837	0.5837	1795.92	551.66	242.64	686.95	1795.85	551.29	243.03	686.01
0	5	7	person	776.0	546.0	208.0	404.0	775.9	545.3	202.8	403.11	0.9716	0.5837	0.5837	775.85	545.65	205.4	403.55	775.86	545.71	205.84	403.35
0	6	2	person	80.5	521.5	161.0	867.0	77.09	527.06	154.18	632.86	0.699	0.5837	0.5837	78.79	524.28	157.59	740.93	79.08	523.82	158.16	696.4

Figure 17: Case 2 Test 2 Summary of Detection, Predicted, Corrected, IoU, Kalman gain values, etc.

Figure 18: Case 2 Test 2 Time Series Comparison Plots


```

Total number of frames: 338
Loaded latest CSV file: iou_tracking_data_20250418_025631.csv

===== Normalized MSE Summary =====
MSE (Center X): 0.000052
MSE (Center Y): 0.000156
MSE (Width): 0.000186
MSE (Height): 0.000952
Overall Normalized MSE: 0.000337

```

Figure 20: Case 2 Test 2 Summary of MSE Values

Figure 19: Case 2 Test 2 Pearson's Correlation Between YOLO, Kalman, Corrected, and Fused Variables

RESULTS SUMMARY

Figures 6, 11, and 16 show clearly that the algorithm correctly detects, counts, and tracks object movements. At the top-left-hand corner of the figure, we can see that the count of objects in red was accurate. Similarly, the bounding boxes (Green for YOLO detection, red for Kalman prediction, and Blue for corrected/updated). These bounding boxes (Green and Red) look almost the same i.e. (complete overlap), but slight differences can be observed due to noise and other uncertainties. However, the prediction is still very close to the YOLO detection. Still, the corrected /updated version, i.e., the blue-color box, accurately captures what could not be captured in the detected and corrected version. Also, the yellow lines show the trajectory of objects as they move from frame to frame until the video runs to the end. These trajectories are indicators of the tracks or paths followed by individual objects.

Figures 7, 12, and 17 show the summary of detection, predicted, corrected, IoU and Kalman gain values, etc. Based on the data from the CSV. The following are the observations found.

1. Object Consistency

The tracker consistently follows a single object (Track_ID = 0) labeled as "person" across all entries, showing stable ID assignment and accurate classification. This is true for Figures 7, 12, and 17, the scenarios of Live video, tested, and recorded videos. For example, in case 2, a recorded video shows football players and a football. We can see clearly that the football tracking ID = 1 remains consistent throughout the video playback. The tracker is consistently showing that the Kalman filter tracks well.

2. Kalman Gain (K_x and K_y): K_x and K_y are observed to be equal for each frame because our Kalman filter uses symmetric matrices and equal noise settings, assuming identical behavior in both x and y directions. This trend was also consistent when the algorithm was tested on live and pre-recorded video. As seen in Figures 7, 12, and 17. Also, Kalman Gain (K_x , K_y) is within the range of **0.41–0.59**, a sign of dynamic balance, i.e., the algorithm balances trust in both YOLO and Kalman prediction. This is a good general-purpose configuration. These values reflect a practical balance between stability and responsiveness.

3. IoU Scores

Most IoU values seen from the CSV file are around **0.85-0.99**, which shows a substantial overlap between YOLO detection and Kalman prediction. This reflects high tracking accuracy in the approach adopted in this project. Although minor drops (e.g., to ~0.89) occur occasionally when there's a brief deviation.

In Case 1 (Live video test experiment) and Case 2 (Pre-recorded video experiment test 1 and 2), the average IoU values recorded based on data from figures 7, 12, and 17 are:

Table 4: Average IoU Values Calculated Per Experiment

Average IoU (Live Video Object Tracking Test)	Average IoU (Pre-recorded Video Object Tracking Test 1)	Average IoU (Pre-recorded Video Object Tracking Test 2)
0.9073	0.8533	0.8777

4. Kalman Corrected/Updated results after prediction and comparison with the linear fusion method

Lastly, the Kalman filter adaptively adjusts how much it trusts the prediction vs. the new measurement at every step to obtain the correction/updated desired results. We also compared this corrected value with the results of the fusion method (linear blending of YOLO detection and Kalman predictions). The Kalman update approach still yields desirable results. It applies mainly to tracking applications such as motion predictions, robotics, or control systems unlike the fusion method, which can still carry some inertial from frames, causing ghost effects or delay. Hence, the fusion method can introduce some uncertainties during blending, despite its accuracy.

Figures 8, 13, and 18 show the time series comparison between YOLO detection and Kalman prediction; these plots show how the objects' centers (X, Y) change over time.

A. YOLO (Top Row):

High variance (esp. in CX): indicates YOLO sometimes fluctuates when detecting the exact object center.

B. Kalman Predictions (Middle Row):

Because Kalman filters out noisy measurements, the Kalman prediction appears smoother than YOLO. As seen in the middle row, periods of sharp transitions correlate with object movement or detection gaps.

C. Combined Plots (Bottom Row):

The green and orange lines (YOLO vs Kalman) mostly overlap, but Kalman is slightly smoother and lags minimally when YOLO jitters. The structural difference is almost negligible but still visible.

We can conclude from these observations that the Kalman filter not only helps to improve temporal consistency but also helps to stabilize the jittery YOLO detections.

From **figures 9, 14, and 19**, which show correlation heatmaps, it's clear that the Kalman Filter does a great job tracking the object's horizontal position (center X), with strong agreement between its predictions and YOLO's detections. Vertical tracking (center Y) is fairly consistent, though not always perfect. The object's width shows some variability, while height is the least consistent, probably because the filter treats it as fixed. Overall, the filter is solid for tracking where the object is. Weak correlations between various bounding box parameters (such as CX and W) in the heatmap suggest that these characteristics are usually independent, which is generally a good sign. Kalman Corrected is theoretically the most accurate estimate when the model and noise are adequately defined. Hence, it is statistically optimal since it is based on probabilistic weighting, whereas the fusion method is not statistically optimal.

Figures 10, 15, and 20 show the MSE values recorded for different scenarios as listed in **Table 5**. We can see that the MSE values are almost zero. Hence, the MSE in each case is kept as small as possible. This also supports the paper's contribution that the algorithm produces the best results.

Table 5: MSE Values recorded

MSE (Live Video Object Tracking Test)		MSE (Pre-recorded Video Object Tracking Test 1)		MSE (Pre-recorded Video Object Tracking Test 2)	
Normalized MSE Summary		Normalized MSE Summary		Normalized MSE Summary	
Metric	Value	Metric	Value	Metric	Value
MSE (Center X)	0.000017	MSE (Center X)	0.000002	MSE (Center X)	0.000052
MSE (Center Y)	0.000040	MSE (Center Y)	0.000004	MSE (Center Y)	0.000156
MSE (Width)	0.000041	MSE (Width)	0.000007	MSE (Width)	0.000186
MSE (Height)	0.000175	MSE (Height)	0.000010	MSE (Height)	0.000952
Overall	0.000068	Overall	0.000006	Overall	0.000337
Normalized MSE		Normalized MSE		Normalized MSE	

DISCUSSION

- YOLO provides accurate and fast detections but exhibits jitters and other inconsistencies across frames.
- The Kalman Filter smooths detections, even during brief losses or occlusion; its predictions are still stable and accurate.
- The time series plots also show a strong alignment between the Yolo detection and the predictions from the Kalman filtering process.
- The low MSE values recorded during the project's testing phase show that Kalman predictions closely follow the true detections while filtering out noise.
- The high IoU values recorded also imply that the filter predicts well and preserves spatial accuracy.
- High Pearson scores imply a strong linear relationship. It is also evident that the Kalman filter maintains smooth tracking over time, and reduces ID switching, and trajectory breaks.

CONCLUSION

The approach adopted and implementation results presented in this project show that the combination of YOLO, Kalman filter, and Hungarian algorithm makes an effective, stable, and reliable method of tracking objects in videos. While we have shown that YOLO detects well, the Kalman filter ensures smooth tracking, especially during fast motion and brief occlusion. Ultimately, this approach strikes a solid balance between rapid detection and reliable tracking. Making it suitable for real-world and offline video analysis. Overall, this project confirms the reliability of the Kalman filter in tracking applications.

RELEVANCE OF THIS PROJECT TO THE COURSE (ECE 418)

This project is relevant to this course in the sense that the project directly applies key concepts from ECE 418 (Statistical Digital signal processing) such as statistical modeling, estimation theory, error evaluation techniques (such as MSE, IoU), and other statistical similarity measures (such as Pearson's correlation coefficient and Time series comparison plots).

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